

FREQUENCY OF HYPOMAGNESEMIA IN PATIENTS PRESENTING WITH STROKE, TYPE OF STROKE AND SEVERITY AT JPMC, KARACHI

Anjli Tara¹, Dr. Muhammad Omer Sultan², Dr. Muhammad Inam Khan³, Mahnoor Jamal⁴,
Hina Kumari⁵, Dessar Zehra⁶, Aniket Tara⁷

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center

⁷Liaquat University is of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro

¹anjli.tara@gmail.com, ²dr.omersultan@hotmail.com, ³drinam373@gmail.com,

⁴mahnoor.j4123@gmail.com, ⁵kumari.hina17@yahoo.com, ⁶desaarz@gmail.com, ⁷tara.aniket@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15589507>

Keywords

Hypomagnesemia, acute ischemic stroke, stroke severity, NIH Stroke Scale, serum magnesium, ischemic stroke, hemorrhagic stroke, vascular risk factors, smoking, magnesium deficiency, South Asian population.

Article History

Received on 26 April 2025

Accepted on 26 May 2025

Published on 04 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Anjli Tara

Abstract

Background: Magnesium plays an important role in vascular function, neuronal excitability, and metabolic regulation. There is growing interest in the prognostic significance of serum magnesium levels in stroke. However, there is limited data on its association with stroke type, severity, and vascular risk factors among South Asian populations. This study aimed to determine the frequency of hypomagnesemia among patients presenting with stroke and to examine its relationship with stroke subtype, severity, and comorbid conditions.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional study at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi. We enrolled 148 adult patients diagnosed with acute stroke. Serum magnesium levels were measured upon admission. Hypomagnesemia was defined as levels below 1.8 mg/dL. We recorded demographic and clinical data, including stroke type, NIH Stroke Scale (NIHSS) score, and comorbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and smoking history. Statistical analysis included chi-square tests to assess associations between hypomagnesemia and categorical variables, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results: Hypomagnesemia was noted among 36.5% of patients. It was significantly more common among those who had ischemic stroke (44.1%) than those who had hemorrhagic stroke (19.6%; $p = 0.01$). A higher prevalence of hypomagnesemia was observed among patients with mild stroke severity (NIHSS 0–6; $p = 0.01$). Smoking status showed a strong association, with 52.7% of smokers affected, compared to 26.9% of non-smokers ($p = 0.01$). Conversely, hypomagnesemia was less prevalent in individuals with hypertension ($p = 0.02$) and dyslipidemia ($p = 0.01$). No significant associations emerged with age, gender, or diabetes.

Conclusions: Our findings indicate that hypomagnesemia frequently affects patients with acute stroke, particularly those with ischemic stroke, mild severity, and smoking history. The inverse association with hypertension and dyslipidemia suggests a complex interplay between magnesium status and vascular risk profiles. Routine assessment of serum magnesium may help identify patients at greater risk of poor outcomes and inform individualized management strategies in acute stroke care.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke ranks as the second most common cause of death globally, responsible for approximately 5.5 million fatalities annually. It is defined as a sudden onset of localized neurological impairment caused by acute infarction of brain tissue within the central nervous system. This condition may lead to symptoms lasting longer than 24 hours or can be fatal within that period.¹⁻³ Pakistan has yet to conduct a comprehensive, large-scale epidemiological study to accurately determine the national incidence of stroke. However, available data suggest that stroke cases are on the rise, especially among younger individuals. Current estimates indicate that approximately 250 people per 100,000 population experience a stroke each year in the country.^{4,6} In Pakistan, the overall average prevalence of stroke is estimated at 1.2%. However, certain studies have reported significantly higher rates in specific populations—for example, among an adult Pashtoon community residing in Karachi, the prevalence has been found to be as high as 4.8%.^{7,8}

One primary mechanism leading to stroke involves bleeding caused by the rupture of a blood vessel, often due to high blood pressure or other vascular abnormalities. This results in a hemorrhagic stroke, which represents approximately 10–20% of stroke cases worldwide.⁹⁻¹⁰ The second major type is ischemic stroke, which occurs when blood flow to the brain is reduced due to either a blocked blood vessel or inadequate perfusion pressure. This leads to localized or widespread brain tissue infarction and accounts for approximately 87% of all stroke cases.⁸ Due to the brain's high metabolic demands and its receipt of 15–20% of the total cardiac output, even a brief disruption in blood supply can result in temporary tissue damage.^{9,11} If the interruption persists, it can trigger a series of complex biochemical events that generate free radicals, ultimately leading to irreversible neuronal death.¹²⁻¹⁵

Magnesium (Mg) is a vital mineral that plays a key role in more than 300 enzymatic processes. It is essential for the synthesis and stability of ATP, DNA, and RNA, and it also supports the structural integrity of ribosomes, which are crucial for protein production.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Magnesium has been shown to offer protective benefits against stroke, primarily through its role in regulating blood pressure—one of the

major risk factors for stroke. Furthermore, magnesium contributes to stroke prevention by lowering the risk of metabolic syndrome, reducing platelet aggregation, and improving endothelial function.^{19,20} Low magnesium levels, or hypomagnesemia, can contribute to endothelial injury by promoting oxidative stress and triggering inflammatory responses, thereby negatively impacting cardiovascular health. Additionally, magnesium deficiency can impair the function of the sodium-potassium (Na^+/K^+) pump, which is essential for maintaining proper cellular ion balance.²¹ This impairment can disturb myocardial excitability, exacerbating conditions like atrial fibrillation, a significant risk factor for embolism and stroke.²² Magnesium also plays a critical role in maintaining blood-brain barrier integrity, reducing edema after stroke, and increasing antioxidants in the affected area by stimulating antioxidant enzymes.²³ It also blocks NMDA receptors during excitotoxicity in acute ischemic stroke. Conversely, low Mg levels can worsen the condition of the penumbral region, leading to more severe stroke presentations. Research has shown that low Mg levels are associated with an increased risk of thrombosis, further highlighting its importance in stroke prevention.^{24,25} Samavarch et al found the prevalence of hypomagnesemia in stroke patients to be 56.1%. We also observed that 36.9% of the ischemic stroke patients and 76.7% of those having the hemorrhagic type had hypomagnesemia.²⁶ Hypomagnesemia, characterized by low serum magnesium levels, has been implicated in various pathophysiological processes, including neurovascular dysfunction, inflammation, and oxidative stress, which are critical in the development and progression of stroke. Despite its known role in vascular health, the prevalence of hypomagnesemia among stroke patients, particularly in relation to different stroke subtypes (ischemic, hemorrhagic) and stroke severity, remains underexplored. Understanding the frequency and patterns of hypomagnesemia in this population could provide valuable insights into its potential role as a modifiable risk factor, prognostic marker, or therapeutic target. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the prevalence of hypomagnesemia in stroke patients, examining associations with stroke

type and severity, and exploring its implications for clinical outcomes, thereby contributing to improved management strategies and risk stratification in stroke care.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was carried out over a six-month period in the Department of Medicine at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi, following ethical clearance from the institutional review board and approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan. The study included 148 patients, based on a sample size calculated using WHO software with a 56.1% estimated prevalence of hypomagnesemia in stroke patients, a 7% margin of error, and a 95% confidence interval. Patients were selected through a non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Participants included individuals aged between 40 and 70 years of either gender, who are admitted within 24 hours of experiencing symptoms of stroke and have confirmation of stroke via a plain CT brain scan. Exclusion criteria include patients with a known history of hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, pregnancy (confirmed via history and dating scan), or those diagnosed with central nervous system disorders such as head trauma or multiple sclerosis. Additionally, patients with comorbidities like asthma, renal failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, congestive heart failure, myocardial infarction, chronic liver disease, malignancy, tuberculosis, meningitis, encephalitis, or hydrocephalus were not included.

Informed consent—both verbal and written—was obtained from the patients or their attendants after explaining the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study. Once enrolled, each patient will undergo a detailed clinical evaluation and physical examination, including a structured neurological assessment to measure stroke severity using the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS). This neurological exam was assessed various parameters, such as level of consciousness, basic orientation questions (month and age), ability to blink eyes and squeeze hands, eye movements, visual fields, facial symmetry, motor strength in all limbs, coordination, sensation, speech clarity, language comprehension, and signs of inattention or neglect.

The NIHSS score was computed and categorized based on predefined score ranges.

Blood samples were collected under aseptic conditions using a sterile 5 ml syringe and sent to the hospital's laboratory to determine serum magnesium levels. A magnesium level of ≤ 1.5 g/dL was used to define hypomagnesemia. All study data, including clinical findings, NIHSS scores, stroke type, and biochemical results, was recorded in a structured proforma prepared for this study.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS Version 22. Quantitative variables such as age and NIHSS scores were evaluated for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Normally distributed variables were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation, while skewed data was reported as medians with interquartile ranges. Qualitative variables such as gender, presence of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, dyslipidemia, smoking status, stroke type, NIHSS score category, and hypomagnesemia status were presented as frequencies and percentages. To identify the influence of potential confounding factors, stratification was carried out for variables like age, gender, diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidemia, smoking, stroke type, and NIHSS categories. Post-stratification, chi-square or Fisher's exact test was applied where appropriate, with a p-value of ≤ 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

This study included 148 patients diagnosed with stroke. Most participants (68.9%) were between 56 and 70 years old, while the remaining 31.1% were aged 40 to 55 years. Women made up a slightly higher proportion of the cohort (53.4%) compared to men (46.6%).

Ischemic stroke was the predominant type, occurring in 68.9% of patients, whereas 31.1% experienced hemorrhagic stroke. Based on the NIH Stroke Scale (NIHSS), 22.3% of patients had mild strokes (score 0–6), 38.5% had moderate strokes (score 7–15), and 39.2% presented with severe strokes (score ≥ 16).

Regarding comorbidities, 30.4% of participants had diabetes mellitus, and 23% had hypertension. Dyslipidemia was present in 42.6% of the sample, and 37.2% reported a history of smoking. Hypomagnesemia, defined as serum magnesium

levels below the clinical threshold, was identified in 36.5% of patients.

We examined associations between hypomagnesemia and clinical characteristics. The prevalence of hypomagnesemia did not differ significantly by age group ($p = 0.77$) or gender ($p = 0.68$). However, patients with ischemic stroke exhibited a notably higher rate of hypomagnesemia (44.1%) compared to those with hemorrhagic stroke (19.6%), and this difference reached statistical significance ($p = 0.01$).

Stroke severity showed a significant relationship with magnesium levels. Among those with hypomagnesemia, 57.6% had mild strokes, while 26.3% had moderate and 34.5% had severe strokes ($p = 0.01$), indicating that patients with lower NIHSS scores were more likely to have low magnesium levels.

Hypertension was less common among patients with hypomagnesemia (20.6%) than among those with normal magnesium levels (41.2%, $p = 0.02$). Conversely, dyslipidemia appeared significantly more prevalent in patients without hypomagnesemia (51.8%) than those with it (15.9%, $p = 0.01$). Smokers were also more likely to exhibit hypomagnesemia (52.7%) compared to non-smokers (26.9%), and this association was statistically significant ($p = 0.01$). We found no significant difference in the frequency of hypomagnesemia between diabetic and non-diabetic patients ($p = 0.59$).

Taken together, these findings suggest that hypomagnesemia is more frequently observed in patients with ischemic stroke, a history of smoking, and those presenting with less severe strokes. However, it appears to be less common among individuals with hypertension or dyslipidemia.

DISCUSSION

This study noted the prevalence of hypomagnesemia among stroke patients. We also explored the association of hypomagnesemia with stroke type, severity, and common vascular risk factors. Our study found that over one-third of the patients had low serum magnesium levels. This trend is consistent with previous studies which were conducted in South Asian hospital settings.²⁷⁻²⁹

Hypomagnesemia appeared significantly more common among patients presenting with ischemic

stroke compared to hemorrhagic stroke. This finding reinforces earlier research suggesting that magnesium depletion may play a more prominent role in ischemic pathophysiology, possibly due to its influence on endothelial function, vasodilation, and pro-thrombotic mechanisms.³⁰⁻³² The relatively lower frequency among hemorrhagic cases may reflect different underlying vascular processes that are less sensitive to magnesium fluctuations.

Interestingly, a greater proportion of patients with lower NIHSS scores, which is typically indicative of milder strokes, had hypomagnesemia. This contrasts with assumptions that more severe clinical presentations would correlate with greater metabolic derangement. However, similar trends have been reported in earlier observational studies, where patients with mild ischemic strokes and low magnesium levels. These in turn had demonstrated worse long-term functional outcomes. It is possible that magnesium deficiency influences stroke recovery more than initial severity, perhaps by impairing neuroplasticity, delaying reperfusion, or increasing the risk of secondary complications.³³⁻³⁴

Our data had also identified a strong association between hypomagnesemia and smoking. Over half of the smokers in our cohort exhibited low magnesium levels. This aligned with literature that links tobacco use to increased renal magnesium excretion and chronic oxidative stress.³⁵⁻³⁶ This finding suggests that smoking may exacerbate pre-existing mineral imbalances, potentially amplifying the neurological impact of ischemia.

We observed an inverse association between hypomagnesemia and both hypertension and dyslipidemia. This result differs from prior studies where low magnesium levels often co-occurred with chronic metabolic conditions.³⁷⁻³⁸ One possible explanation could be our sample. Our sample comprised of patients with longstanding hypertension or dyslipidemia may have been receiving regular care, dietary counseling, or pharmacological treatments that inadvertently supported magnesium balance. However, the possibility of residual confounding cannot be ruled out.

We found no significant differences in hypomagnesemia rates based on age, gender, or diabetes status. These findings are consistent with

earlier studies from both local and international settings,⁴⁰ where demographic variables did not show a strong influence on magnesium levels among stroke patients. Although diabetes is commonly associated with hypomagnesemia in the general population [14], our cohort's relatively modest number of diabetic individuals may have limited our ability to detect this association.

These data suggest that serum magnesium may serve as a relevant clinical marker in the acute evaluation of stroke. This is particularly so for ischemic cases and individuals with certain behavioral risk factors such as smoking. Recent researches have questioned the efficacy of intravenous magnesium for acute stroke management.⁴⁰ Our findings, however, add to the growing body of evidence supporting magnesium's potential as a prognostic biomarker.

Further prospective studies are warranted to clarify whether magnesium repletion could offer benefits in post-stroke recovery. Particularly among patients with initially mild symptoms or modifiable lifestyle risks.

LIMITATIONS

This study design limited our ability to establish causal relationships between hypomagnesemia and

stroke severity. We recruited patients from a single center using non-probability sampling, which may have introduced selection bias. We did not collect data on dietary intake or medications that could influence serum magnesium levels. By excluding patients with chronic comorbidities, we may have reduced the broader applicability of our findings. We also relied on a single magnesium measurement, which may not reflect long-term magnesium status.

CONCLUSION

We identified a high frequency of hypomagnesemia among patients with acute stroke, particularly in those with ischemic stroke, mild neurological deficits, and a history of smoking. These findings highlight a potential role for magnesium as a clinical marker in the early evaluation of stroke. The inverse associations with hypertension and dyslipidemia raise important questions about the metabolic context of magnesium regulation in cerebrovascular disease. By including serum magnesium in the initial assessment, clinicians may be able to identify patients at greater risk of poor outcomes. Further studies should explore whether addressing magnesium deficiency could influence recovery and long-term prognosis after stroke.

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
40 to 55 years	46 (31.1)
56 to 70 years	102 (68.9)
Gender	
Male	69 (46.6)
Female	79 (53.4)
Type of stroke	
Ischemic	102 (68.9)
Hemorrhagic	46 (31.1)
NIHSS score category	
NIHSS score 0-6	33 (22.3)
NIHSS score 7-15	57 (38.5)
NIHSS score ≥16	58 (39.2)
Diabetes Mellitus	
Yes	45 (30.4)
No	103 (69.6)
Hypertension	
Yes	34 (23)
No	114 (77)

Dyslipidemia	
Yes	63 (42.6)
No	85 (57.4)
Smoking status	
Yes	55 (37.2)
No	93 (62.8)
Hypomagnesemia	
Yes	54 (36.5)
No	94 (63.5)
Total	148 (100)

Table 2: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the Hypomagnesemia.

Variables	Hypomagnesemia Yes n (%)	Hypomagnesemia No n (%)	P value
Age			0.77
40 to 55 years	16 (34.8)	30 (65.2)	
56 to 70 years	38 (37.3)	64 (62.7)	
Gender			0.68
Male	24 (34.8)	45 (65.2)	
Female	30 (38)	49 (62)	
Type of stroke			0.01
Ischemic	45 (44.1)	57 (55.9)	
Hemorrhagic	09 (19.6)	37 (80.4)	
NIHSS score category			0.01
NIHSS score 0-6	19 (57.6)	14 (42.4)	
NIHSS score 7-15	15 (26.3)	42 (73.7)	
NIHSS score ≥16	20 (34.5)	38 (65.5)	
Diabetes Mellitus			0.59
Yes	15 (33.3)	30 (66.7)	
No	39 (37.9)	64 (62.1)	
Hypertension			0.02
Yes	07 (20.6)	27 (79.4)	
No	47 (41.2)	67 (58.8)	
Dyslipidemia			0.01
Yes	10 (15.9)	53 (84.1)	
No	44 (51.8)	41 (48.2)	
Smoking status			0.01
Yes	29 (52.7)	26 (47.3)	
No	25 (26.9)	68 (73.1)	

REFERENCES:

Sacco RL, Kasner SE, Broderick JP, Caplan LR, Connors JJ, Culebras A et al. An updated definition of stroke for the 21st century: a statement for healthcare professionals from the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association. *Stroke*. 2013 Jul;44(7):2064-89.

Sorensen AG, Ay H. Transient ischemic attack: definition, diagnosis, and risk stratification. *Neuro Clin* 2011 May 1;21(2):303-13.

Murphy SJ, Werring DJ. Stroke: causes and clinical features. *Medicine (Abingdon)* 48: 561-566.

Donkor ES. Stroke in the 21st century: a snapshot of the burden, epidemiology, and quality of life. *Stroke Res Treat*. 2018;2018(1):3238165.

- Feigin VL, Brainin M, Norrving B, Martins S, Sacco RL, Hacke W et al. World Stroke Organization (WSO): global stroke fact sheet 2022. *Intern J Stroke*. 2022 Jan;17(1):18-29.
- Chung CP. Types of stroke and their differential diagnosis. In *Primer on Cerebrovascular Diseases 2017* Jan 1 (pp. 372-376). Academic Press.
- Ojaghiahghighi S, Vahdati SS, Mikaeilpour A, Ramouz A. Comparison of neurological clinical manifestation in patients with hemorrhagic and ischemic stroke. *World J Emerg Med*. 2017;8(1):34-38.
- Chandra A, Stone CR, Du X, Li WA, Huber M, Bremer R et al. The cerebral circulation and cerebrovascular disease III: Stroke. *Brain Circ* 2017 Apr 1;3(2):66-77.
- Sanderson TH, Reynolds CA, Kumar R, Przyklenk K, Hüttemann M. Molecular mechanisms of ischemia-reperfusion injury in brain: pivotal role of the mitochondrial membrane potential in reactive oxygen species generation. *Molecular Neurobiol* 2013 Feb;47:9-23.
- Daniele G, DiLucia S, Masci PG, Del Monte F. Heart and brain: complex relationships for left ventricular dysfunction. *Current Cardiol Rep*. 2020 Aug;22:1-1.
- Li MH, Inoue K, Si HF, Xiong ZG. Calcium-permeable ion channels involved in glutamate receptor-independent ischemic brain injury. *Acta Pharmacologica Sinica*. 2011 Jun;32(6):734-40.
- Wang C, Nguyen HN, Maguire JL, Perry DC. Role of intracellular calcium stores in cell death from oxygen-glucose deprivation in a neuronal cell line. *J Cerebral Blood Flow Metab* 2002 Feb;22(2):206-14.
- Miller LP, Jelovich LA, Yao L, DaRe J, Ugarkar B, Foster AC. Pre-and peristroke treatment with the adenosine kinase inhibitor, 5'-deoxyiodotubercidin, significantly reduces infarct volume after temporary occlusion of the middle cerebral artery in rats. *Neurosci Letters*. 1996 Dec 13;220(2):73-6.
- Almekhlafi MA, Alghamdi AA, Bala F. Risk of Embolization During Carotid Revascularization Procedures and The Role of Neuroimaging. *J Neurosonol Neuro* 2020 Jun 26;12(1):1-9.
- Ciacciarelli A, Sette G, Giubilei F, Orzi F. Chronic cerebral hypoperfusion: An undefined, relevant entity. *J Clin Neurosci* 2020 Mar 1;73:8-12.
- Sherin A, Ul-Haq Z, Fazid S, Shah BH, Khattak MI, Nabi F. Prevalence of stroke in Pakistan: Findings from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa integrated population health survey (KP-IPHS) 2016-17. *Pak J Med Sci* 2020 Nov;36(7):1435.
- Farooq A, Venketasubramanian N, Wasay M. Stroke care in Pakistan. *Cerebrovasc Dis Extra*. 2021 Dec 27;11(3):118-21.
- Gönüllü H, Karadaş S, Milanlioğlu A, Gönüllü E, Celal K, Demir H. Levels of serum trace elements in ischemic stroke patients. *J Exp Clin Med* 2014; 30: 301-4
- Fiorentini D, Cappadone C, Farruggia G, Prata C. Magnesium: biochemistry, nutrition, detection, and social impact of diseases linked to its deficiency. *Nutrients*. 2021 Mar 30;13(4):1136.
- Nie ZL, Wang ZM, Zhou B, Tang ZP, Wang SK. Magnesium intake and incidence of stroke: Meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Nutrition Metab Cardiovasc Dis* 2013;23(3), 169–176.
- Liotta EM, Prabhakaran S, Sangha RS, Bush RA, Long AE, Trevick SA, Potts MB, Jahromi BS, Kim M, Manno EM, Sorond FA. Magnesium, hemostasis, and outcomes in patients with intracerebral hemorrhage. *Neurol* 2017 Aug 22;89(8):813-9.
- Tehrani SS, Khatami SH, Saadat P, Sarfi M, Ahangar AA, Daroie R, Firouzjahi A, Maniati M. Association of serum magnesium levels with risk factors, severity and prognosis in ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke patients. *Caspian J Intern Med* 2020;11(1):83.
- Amir A, Hassan M, Alvi S, Mueed A, Idrees S, Ashraf J et al. Frequency and characteristics of metabolic syndrome in patients with ischemic stroke admitted to a tertiary Care Hospital in Karachi. *Cureus*. 2020 Jul;12(7).
- Hossain MF, Hasan MN, Uddin SM, Masum AA, Basak PM. Serum Magnesium Level among the Patients Admitted with Acute Stroke in a

- Tertiary care Hospital. *J Teachers Ass* 2014;27(1):50-6.
- Murphy SJ, Werring DJ. Stroke: causes and clinical features. *Medicine*. 2023 Jul 25.
- Samavarch TS, Khatami SH, Saadat P. Association of serum magnesium levels with risk factors, severity and prognosis in ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke patients. *Caspian J Intern Med* 2020;11(1):83-91.
- Khanum M, Arshad U, Shakir HA, Arshad II M, Safi I, Shakir Sr HA. Frequency of Hypomagnesemia and Its Relationship With Severity Among Patients of Acute Ischemic Stroke Presenting to a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Cureus*. 2024 Apr 14;16(4).
- Ryu H, Ahn SY, Kim CK, Oh K, Han JH, Lee DW, Kim SH, Kim HJ. Hypomagnesemia as a prognostic marker of ischemic stroke. *Journal of Neurocritical Care*. 2022 Apr 27;15(1):39-45.
- Khan KM, Naeem F, Iqbal R, Shah ZH, Ali R, Gilani N. To determine the frequency of hypomagnesemia among patients with acute ischemic stroke and to study the correlation of serum magnesium with modified Rankin scale after acute ischemic stroke. *Pakistan J Med Health Sci*. 2015 Oct 1;9:1240-3.
- Ohira T, Peacock JM, Iso H, Chambless LE, Rosamond WD, Folsom AR. Serum and dietary magnesium and risk of ischemic stroke: the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2009 Jun 15;169(12):1437-44.
- Barbagallo M, Dominguez LJ, Galioto A, Ferlisi A, Cani C, Malfa L, Pineo A, Paolisso G. Role of magnesium in insulin action, diabetes and cardio-metabolic syndrome X. *Molecular aspects of medicine*. 2003 Feb 6;24(1-3):39-52.
- Muir KW, Lees KR, Ford I, Davis S. Intravenous magnesium efficacy in stroke (IMAGES) study investigators. Magnesium for acute stroke (intravenous magnesium efficacy in stroke trial): randomised controlled trial. *Lancet*. 2004;363(9407):439-45.
- Kumar A, Mehan S, Tiwari A, Khan Z, Das Gupta G, Narula AS, Samant R. Magnesium (Mg²⁺): Essential mineral for neuronal health: From cellular biochemistry to cognitive health and behavior regulation. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*. 2024 Nov;30(39):3074-107.
- Afshari D, Moradian N, Rezaei M. Evaluation of the intravenous magnesium sulfate effect in clinical improvement of patients with acute ischemic stroke. *Clinical neurology and neurosurgery*. 2013 Apr 1;115(4):400-4.
- Guerrero-Romero F, Rodriguez-Moran M. Low serum magnesium levels and metabolic syndrome. *Acta diabetologica*. 2002 Dec;39:209-13.
- Durlach J. Recommended dietary amounts of magnesium: Mg RDA. *Magnesium research*. 1989 Sep 1;2(3):195-203.
- Ford ES, Mokdad AH. Dietary magnesium intake in a national sample of US adults. *The Journal of nutrition*. 2003 Sep 1;133(9):2879-82.
- Ma J, Folsom AR, Melnick SL, Eckfeldt JH, Sharrett AR, Nabulsi AA, Hutchinson RG, Metcalf PA. Associations of serum and dietary magnesium with cardiovascular disease, hypertension, diabetes, insulin, and carotid arterial wall thickness: the ARIC study. *Journal of clinical epidemiology*. 1995 Jul 1;48(7):927-40.
- Pham PC, Pham PM, Pham SV, Miller JM, Pham PT. Hypomagnesemia in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Clinical journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 2007 Mar 1;2(2):366-73.
- Saver JL, Starkman S. Magnesium in clinical stroke. In: *Magnesium in the Central Nervous System*. University of Adelaide Press, Adelaide (AU); 2011. PMID: 29920001.